

Establish governance rules for new ESiWACE developments Milestone MS3

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Introduction and context

Effective governance necessitates intense exchange within and beyond the community. We have noted in the ESIWACE proposal (Sec. 1.3.3) that *“networking activities depend on the community’s maturity in a given area. In some areas we can build on previous activities around established shared software especially from IS-ENES2. This includes the evaluation of coupling technologies and the support of the OASIS coupler, the development of I/O strategies, the development and support of the XIOS I/O server and the Cylc workflow engine, common analyses of model codes such as NEMO and EC-Earth. In this case networking for existing community software will foster community co-operation based on an agreed set of benchmarks and will drive continued research towards improvement of these tool through engagement with the existing user community. Dissemination of community software will be enhanced by improved user support and training as well as fastest possible integration of new software versions.*

In other areas, the community’s maturity is lower and will focus on networking for new community software with activities supporting to share specialist knowledge that exists but is not yet available across the community. An example is the development of suitable software stacks for HPC systems.”

Central goal of ESIWACE is to improve efficiency and productivity for weather and climate simulations in view of upcoming exa-scale computing and data handling systems. New software developments arise in this context, besides supporting and improving existing software solutions.

During the ESIWACE General Assembly meeting in July 2016, the consortium agreed to focus on the implementation and analysis of demonstrators for very high resolution Earth System Models in order to identify gaps between current and expected exa-scale weather and climate simulations and, correspondingly, prioritise developments. These demonstrators shall yield insights into computability of weather and climate codes in the era of exa-scale computing. Hence, they shall provide evidence to develop a roadmap for driving climate and weather simulation towards exa-scale. The interest in the demonstrator development is significant, which has recently been confirmed by a survey on community software development: 80% of non-ESiWACE members (scientific and industrial institutions) who participated in this survey stated that they want to be (regularly) informed on the ESIWACE demonstrator developments.

Definitions and Goals

This milestone closes task 1.1.3 of ESIWACE which had the goals to:

- *“Establish governance rules for new ESIWACE developments; it will define stages of development and review process by users.*
- *Apply a user-driven approach and collect users scientific and technical requests and problems regarding their applications / tools; this will involve partners, supporting partners and, when relevant, computing centres where applications are deployed.”* (ESiWACE amendment, Sec. 3.1.1)

To account for networking within and beyond the community, **this milestone document suggests governance rules for new software** that is developed in the scope of ESIWACE. The governance in place for existing software packages was indicated in ESIWACE deliverable D1.1 “Agreed portfolio of community tools” and is **not** addressed in this document. **In the present scope, we define “new software development” as development of (completely or partly new) software, software components or software concepts that significantly contribute to scientific findings and innovations of ESIWACE.** New developments may thus also arise in the scope of existing software (e.g., the development of a new submodule for an existing climate model). The software development within ESIWACE is community driven from the point of view of identifying scientific needs, requirements, quality, ease of use and performance within the limits of available effort. To establish the suggested

rules we have engaged the community through a survey in the form of a questionnaire (see section “Involving the ESIWACE community”) that was sent to all ESIWACE partners to reflect their interest.

Our suggestions are meant to:

- (1) **guarantee that new software developments which are deemed to be relevant for the larger Earth System Modelling community within the weather and climate domain are coordinated**, i.e. new approaches, information on ongoing developments and respective results are rapidly shared within the community as well as with the “*strategic scientists within our institutions*” who are responsible for “*establishing technical directions and decision making in ESIWACE*” from “*above*” (List of questions to be addressed by HPC CoE projects¹),
- (2) **guarantee that users are involved in new software developments** of ESIWACE (user driven approach),
- (3) **enable control and reflection on ongoing and planned new software developments**, in the sense that new developments are critically evaluated within and beyond ESIWACE.

“A one-size-fits-all approach to governance would be ineffective” with regard to the main challenges of ESIWACE, cf. the list of questions to be addressed by HPC CoE projects¹. This also holds for innovative software developments which are based on various pieces of software (with different governance structures already in place in case of existing, e.g. community, software; information on community software has been collected from all relevant community institutions in a separate survey early 2017, see section below) and on different subproblem settings (e.g., workflows, high-resolution simulations, software stacks). This heterogeneity thus needs to be taken into consideration.

Adaption of the governance rules may be required in the future due to potentially evolving needs by the community or due to changes arising from the emerging exa-scale computing paradigms.

Involvement of the ESIWACE community

To define governance rules for new software developments, we foster exchange with all partners within the ESIWACE consortium. Each partner’s interest, goals, needs and future perspective on innovative software developments should be reflected by the governance rules as well as possible. This will guarantee that the software development within ESIWACE follows the governance guidelines, and, potentially, even software developments outside ESIWACE may be influenced, since the size and composition of the consortium is representative for an even larger group within climate and weather modelling. Furthermore, it will guarantee the effectiveness of the approach and imply a stronger identification of all members with the developments.

Two surveys were created and sent to all ESIWACE partners. The first one focussed on community software and the second one on new ESIWACE software developments. The latter questionnaire (cf. **Appendix**) consisted of three parts on:

- (A) Which kind of software is considered by the partner in the new developments,
- (B) What relation exists between the developments and the demonstrator development,
- (C) General aspects concerning shared development and software governance.

¹ <http://www.esiwace.eu/results/misc/annex-on-hpc-and-cppp/view>

Overview: New software developments in ESIWACE

The spectrum of new software developments in ESIWACE (cf. (A)) is—as defined in the proposal and the annex sections 1-3—broad, which is partly due to the ambitious goal of establishing the very high-resolution demonstrators. To name a few examples, workflow and scripting environments have to be reshaped, workflow management is revised and further developed (reflected in terms of the software Cylc), and the EC-Earth framework is extended by integrating OpenIFS. Moreover, a completely new I/O middleware for climate/weather data and tools for estimating costs and performance of various I/O architectures are developed, as well as libraries to enhance tape storage (cf. work package 4). Besides, various existing software packages are being extended by new components and developments, for example the data management and I/O software XIOS, or the coupling software (OASIS-MCT, YAC) targeting the large-scale atmosphere-ocean demonstrators. Last but not least we will evaluate and employ new concepts, for example using reduced precision representation of variable in Earth System Models to improve efficiency and performance.

This goes along with different licensing concepts (cf. (C)). Although most software is open-source/under LGPL/CeCILL licensing, other, potentially stricter, licensing concepts apply, for example, to (Open)IFS (ECMWF). This also reflects different kinds of governance that have been established for the considered software packages, or that will be established in the future.

The variety in software and potential restrictions in its usage thus need to be taken into account when formulating governance concepts for the new ESIWACE developments.

Survey evaluation

The broad spectrum of answers concerning software (A) also yields specific needs for the different ongoing software developments and involved partners, and it reflects the different kinds of what has to be faced. Although the new software developments jointly contribute to ESIWACE goals, their potential may reach out beyond one or the other community. An example is given by the development of new tape access strategies and new disk storage layouts (cf. work package 4), which may become of great relevance for handling of big data in general.

The community is further clearly aware of the fact that weather and climate simulation at exa-scale require (amongst others):

- robust and evolved software that goes even beyond the ESIWACE demonstrators,
- enhanced I/O and data management strategies, within (potentially coupled) models as well as within the workflow engines,
- effective means to support the software development, for example in form of debugging tools for massively parallel applications.

Concerning the latter, the feedback from the consortium partners also clearly demonstrated that synergies within the consortium, in particular the expertise by Allinea on parallel software development and debugging, should be further exploited and fostered.

Although the challenges from above require a highly interdisciplinary consortium (as it is the case in ESiWACE), the expertise required in the development of the high-resolution demonstrator (B) are rather specific to computer science. From the answers of the questionnaire, three major fields of required expertise could be identified:

- performance and parallelisation,
- data and I/O handling,
- software engineering.

Feedback and exchange with software developers and computing centres is considered most valuable. Concerning the format of the feedback, personal discussion and workshops are the preferred communication channels.

Workshops and personal discussions (including coding days) as well as teleconferences are also considered important in the more generalised context of software development (C). Technical means such as versioning software (git, svn) and issue trackers are ranked important, too and are widely in use. Due to the demonstrator development, performance metrics for computability and data management dominate the list of success indicators in the development process.

From the first survey, it became apparent that the broader user community, counting project supporters from Europe and beyond, alongside partners, has a clear interest in following ESiWACE activities and selected a periodic (monthly to semi-yearly) newsletter as preferred general information channel. Perceived often as a mere outreach mean, periodic dissemination could in turn translate into delivering elements to shape better services to the community when among the supporting institutions advocating for periodic updates on project progress, as it is the case here, there are industrial solution providers.

Governance rules for new software developments

Based on the analysis, the following governance rules for new software developments in ESiWACE result. The governance is strictly user-based (*"The direct users of ESiWACE span the model developers and HPC architects who are preparing for future heterogeneous multi-core HPC developments."* (List of questions to be addressed by HPC CoE projects¹)), which has been and is still considered to be of major importance within the ESiWACE consortium. It is subject to regular internal re-evaluation to keep it aligned with the needs of the ESiWACE consortium.

Person-to-person interaction shall be fostered.

This will be achieved by various means such as the ones discussed above (cf. Section "Survey evaluation") and will contribute to all goals (1)-(3). Mutual exchange visits between the ESiWACE partners are highly encouraged to enable intense exchange on a person-to-person basis. Potential

workshop formats and respective instantiation to enable coordination, user involvement and control for new ESiWACE software developments (goals (1)-(3)) are described in Section “Workshops” below.

New software developments shall be controlled on a regular basis by their developers, the ESiWACE coordination, and the relevant communities.

This particularly addresses goal (3), but also goals (1) and (2). Parallel performance, computability and efficient data management have been identified as major success indicators for the outcomes of the new software developments in ESiWACE. They had been taken into account when preparing the ESiWACE performance indication document and are specifically reflected in the key performance indicators (KPIs) 1, 2, and 6. They are controlled on an annual basis until the end of the project. Further controlling beyond the KPIs in the form of specific considerations to the actual innovative software development are encouraged.

Another means to control new software developments with regard to relevance for the community and originality is presenting the developments and their outcomes in the scope of conferences or workshops (cf. Section “Workshops”) in various communities. This has been and will always be part of the regular ESiWACE agenda.

Upcoming challenges and potentials shall be identified, shared and revisited on a regular basis.

This is accomplished in the scope of ESiWACE communication channels from “*above*” (strategic scientists) and “*below*” (ESiWACE partners and colleagues), cf. the list of questions to be addressed by HPC CoE projects¹ and contributes to reaching goals (1) and (3).

To clarify and to identify prospects on productivity and efficiency of weather and climate simulation in the scope of the demonstrator developments, a collaborative paper will be prepared to outline and discuss potentials for weather and climate modelling at exa-scale. This will provide insights on current challenges and provide future directions for innovative software development within and beyond ESiWACE. It is expected that this will not only be of great relevance for the ESiWACE partners, but also for the global weather and climate modelling communities. Exchange with international experts in the scope of this paper is therefore key.

Workshop formats to enable governance of new software developments

To foster exchange among experts beyond the community as well as within the ESiWACE consortium, the organisation of workshops in conjunction with group work shall be fostered further, besides relying on various other communication and exchange measures that also exist and are invoked as well already by the ESiWACE community. A workshop may comprise one or several group work sessions out of the following three categories: task-driven (focussing on a particular aspect of an ESiWACE task), development-driven (supporting methods in software development), or driven by the actual weather and climate simulation problem as a whole (focussing on the interplay of various technical and scientific aspects). Examples are:

- task-driven:

- workflow development
- high-resolution simulators
- model coupling
- development-driven:
 - tools and best practices in HPC software development
 - handling heterogeneous architectures
 - I/O in HPC: methods and efficient implementations
 - software engineering: challenges and best practices in weather and climate simulation
- driven by the “application-as-a-whole”:
 - challenges on the way to robust and productive weather and climate simulation at exa-scale
 - software stack requirements at exa-scale and consequences for application software
 - workflow handling at exa-scale
 - group reflection: alignment of community needs, external influences and ESIWACE governance

Task-driven sessions can focus on challenges that are specific to the ESIWACE work plan.

Development-driven sessions yield substantial exchange among software developers facing similar issues. This category particularly addresses interaction with HPC industry such as hardware vendors (with regard to, e.g., file systems) or tool developers (such as ESIWACE partner Allinea) and also allows us to define particular tasks that should be addressed in collaboration with/by computing centres/HPC industry partners. Depending on the technical depth of a workshop session, potential licensing restrictions of and existing governance rules for a specific software can be taken into account during the person-to-person and group interactions.

If the workshop topic is relevant to a larger community, a brief workshop report that summarises the outcomes shall be made publicly available. An embedding of the workshop format into other events to enable continuous collaboration beyond the ESIWACE time frame will be subject of discussion in the ESIWACE consortium.

Fixed events to ensure coordinated action

While both task- and development-driven sessions may be organised for small to mid-sized groups, “application-as-a-whole” sessions will engage the whole ESIWACE consortium and also the community of Earth System Modellers within the weather and climate domain. This will allow for intense exchange on multi-faceted topics.

To this end, we will organise one-day workshops including various group work sessions in conjunction with the annual general assemblies. In particular, the perspectives of the software developments within and beyond the ESIWACE time frame will thus be revisited on an annual basis and the governance rules, if necessary, accordingly adjusted.

A well-suited and already established instrument to involve the larger Earth System Modelling community is provided by the ENES HPC workshops. The 5th workshop in this series is planned for early 2018. It will be dedicated to development of and requirement for cloud and eddy resolving Earth System Models and will specifically focus on interaction with non-ESiWACE partners. This will not only sharpen the view on the ongoing ESiWACE developments, but it will also shed light on and keep track of current developments with regard to exa-scale soft- and hardware.

Appendix: Questionnaire Governance Rules for New ESIWACE Developments

Please answer the questions provided below. The blank space can be used directly – shrink/extend it as you require it. Please send back the filled questionnaire via e-mail to Philipp Neumann, neumann@dkrz.de.

A: Which Software

A1) Do you (plan to) develop any new tools/software within this phase of the project ESIWACE

i) as already planned in the original proposal,

ii) according to new/changed plans after having refocused the project on global cloud resolving models (aka "the demonstrators")?

A2) What should be developed in a potential second phase (please keep in mind that a proposal for an ESIWACE2 will be required to "Show progress towards highly scalable, optimised codes and path to exascale")?

B: Relation to demonstrator (deliverables D2.x)

B1) Give a 1-2 sentence description on your software development, e.g. which part of the demonstrator do you focus on, and how do you plan your developments? Indicate an approximate time line and sub-work packages. E.g., "Focus on I/O (ca. 6 months)", "shared memory parallelism (ca. 6 months)".

Remark: The numbers are not to be meant as "We have to finish sub-WP until X", but rather as a rough estimate for us ("What are the major burdens in the community?").

B2) Which expertises do/would you particularly gather to reach your goal, e.g. to setup the demonstrator?

E.g., cloud microphysics expert, vectorization expert, parallelization and topology-aware programming,...

B3) Which particular risks and issues do you currently face or do you expect to be facing during development?

E.g., missing software support for XY, memory issues, data transfer rates, data extraction, ...

B4) Whose feedback would you like to obtain during the development and after finishing the demonstrator?

E.g., from a computer center (performance measurements/network act.), from an application scientist running actual forecasts with the software, from data management services, from industrial partners/PIs/HPC specialists,...

B5) What kind of communication channel would you prefer for the feedback, cf. B4?

E.g., person-to-person discussion, workshop, newsletter, questionnaire, ...

C: General questions regarding (shared) development and governance

C1) What kinds of interaction platforms would you consider ideal with regard to which purpose of the new software development?

E.g., workshop, small group meetings, telephone conference, email, forum, bug-tracking system,...

C2) What kinds of interaction platforms do you already employ or do you find helpful?

C3) What kinds of interaction platforms are not/have turned out to be not suited for your software development? Please give also an explanation why they are not suited.

C4) How would you try to measure success with regard to your software development?

E.g., scalability/efficiency improved by X, node-level performance increased by Y%, X downloads of my software, Y downloads of our data sets, ratio bug fixes/total number of issues

C5) Which steps would you, from the current perspective, take AFTER ESIWACE (phase1) with regard to software development?

E.g., heterogeneous architecture support, improvement of workflow in step X, include the software in production cycle X, buy a new machine because nothing else helps ;-), enrich software by ensemble statistics,...

C6) Do you expect any licensing issues for part of your developments? Please give details.